

A STRUCTURE DESIGN OF CFRP REAR PRESSURE BULKHEAD WITHOUT STIFFENERS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the research on a structure design of CFRP Rear Pressure Bulkhead without stiffeners is finished. According to establish FEA model, the static and buckling analysis are carried out. The results show that the web crack stopper inner the dome skin have a positive influence on improving the buckling performance and stability of the structure. There is no need to arrange extra stiffeners on the dome skin. The design can meet the strength requirement.

1 INTRODUCTION

The bulkhead of aircraft is a structural component which is installed in the fuselage as the interface of the pressurized zone and unpressurized zone that supports the pressure load in the cabin [1]. The pressure bulkhead is considered to be one of the most significant components in aircraft. Pressure bulkheads are installed in the front and back of a pressurized cabin of an aircraft which can maintain the body shape, withstand the pressure load and install equipment. Figure 1 shows the position of pressure bulkhead.

Figure 1 the position of pressure bulkhead

The rear pressure bulkhead of cylindrical cabin is more likely a kind of dome in preference to a flat pressure bulkhead. A hemispherical shell provides an ideal rear dome because of the membrane stresses for a given amount of material at the least. Actually the dome is a cap of hemisphere rather than a whole hemisphere. During this research, the author assumes that the rear pressure bulkhead with the diameter $D=3000\text{mm}$.

2 Governing equations

2.1 Shell theory

The cylindrical shell structure such as skin of fuselage can only withstand the membrane stress due to pressurization load [2].

The hoop tensile load intensity is

$$N_t = PR_c \quad (1)$$

The hoop tensile stress is

$$f_t = \frac{N_t}{t} = \frac{PR_c}{t} \quad (2)$$

The radial displacement is

$$\Delta R = \left(\frac{PR_c^2}{Et}\right)\left(1 - \frac{\mu}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

The longitudinal load is

$$N_x = \frac{PR_c}{2} \quad (4)$$

The longitudinal stress is

$$f_x = \frac{PR_c}{2t} \quad (5)$$

The axial displacement is

$$\Delta L = \left(\frac{PR_c L}{Et}\right)(0.5 - \mu) \quad (6)$$

According to Niu, M. C.[2], the meridian and tangential membrane stress are same for a hemispherical shell structure which is equal to the longitudinal stress of cylindrical stress that could be expressed as:

$$f_t = f_\phi = \frac{PR_c}{2t} \quad (7)$$

Where f_t is the skin tangential stress;

f_ϕ is the skin meridian stress;

P is the internal cabin pressure;

R_c is the radius of the hemispherical shell;

t is the thickness of the hemispherical shell skin

The uniform load applied on the bulkhead is

$$N_{BR} = \frac{PR_c}{2} \cot\phi \quad (8)$$

The compressive load applied on the bulkhead ring due to pressurization load is

$$F_{BR} = \frac{PR_c^2}{2} \cot\phi \quad (9)$$

Where ϕ is the meridian angle of the domed pressure bulkhead.

2.2 Laminate theory

Laminate is a stack of plies with various fiber orientations bonded by a type of matrix which could be epoxy and polyester as liquid resin [3]. The properties of laminated composite materials such as membrane, bending and membrane-bending coupling stiffness matrices, strength, and stiffness can be obtained by classic laminate theory. By using of the basic single ply material properties E_1 , E_2 , G_{12} , ν , calculate the laminate equivalent elastic constants E_x , E_y , ν_{xy} , G_{xy} and get the stress and strain of each plies, then compared with the ply strength X_t , Y_t , X_c , Y_c , S that get the F.I. according to the strength criteria.

The laminate theory assumes that the plate has a small deformation and follows the classic linear elasticity theory Hook's law. The laminated component is assumed to be a thin wall that can be analyzed in a 2D stress system. For an isotropic element, when both f_1 and f_2 are applied on the edges, the relationship between stress and strain could be express as:

$$e_1 = \frac{1}{E}(f_1 - \nu \cdot f_2) \text{ and } e_2 = \frac{1}{E}(f_2 - \nu \cdot f_1) \quad (10)$$

$$f_1 = \frac{1}{1 - \nu^2}(e_1 + \nu \cdot e_2) \text{ and } f_2 = \frac{1}{1 - \nu^2}(e_2 + \nu \cdot e_1) \quad (11)$$

In matrix form

$$\begin{Bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E} & \frac{-\nu}{E} \\ -\frac{\nu}{E} & \frac{1}{E} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ or } \begin{Bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ S_{21} & S_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{1 - \nu^2} & \frac{\nu}{1 - \nu^2} \\ \frac{\nu}{1 - \nu^2} & \frac{1}{1 - \nu^2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{Bmatrix} \text{ or } \begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Where the $[S]$ is the reduced compliance matrix and $[Q]$ is reduced stiffness matrix.

When the shear stress is applied, the equation could be:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f_1 \\ f_2 \\ f_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = [Q] \begin{Bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ e_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ e_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Where

$$Q_{11} = \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \quad Q_{12} = \frac{\nu_{21}E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} \quad Q_{22} = \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}$$

$$Q_{33} = G_{12} = \frac{Q_{11} - Q_{12}}{2} \quad \frac{\nu_{12}}{\nu_{21}} = \frac{E_1}{E_2}$$

Where the matrix $[\bar{Q}]$ is transformed reduced stiffness matrix. Hence,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} f_x \\ f_y \\ f_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & \bar{Q}_{12} & \bar{Q}_{13} \\ \bar{Q}_{21} & \bar{Q}_{22} & \bar{Q}_{23} \\ \bar{Q}_{31} & \bar{Q}_{32} & \bar{Q}_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} e_x \\ e_y \\ e_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} \\ \bar{Q}_{22} \\ \bar{Q}_{33} \\ \bar{Q}_{12} \\ \bar{Q}_{13} \\ \bar{Q}_{23} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} m^4 & n^4 & 2m^2n^2 & 4m^2n^2 \\ n^4 & m^4 & 2m^2n^2 & 4m^2n^2 \\ m^2n^2 & m^2n^2 & -2m^2n^2 & (m^2 - n^2)^2 \\ m^2n^2 & m^2n^2 & m^4 + n^4 & -4m^2n^2 \\ m^3n & -mn^3 & mn^3 - m^3n & 2(mn^3 - m^3n) \\ mn^3 & -m^3n & m^3n - mn^3 & 2(m^3n - mn^3) \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_{11} \\ Q_{22} \\ Q_{12} \\ Q_{33} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

For a laminate, $[ABD]$ matrices could be obtained by:

$$A_{ij} = \sum_{p=1}^N (z_p - z_{p-1}) (\bar{Q}_{ij})_p \quad (17)$$

$$B_{ij} = \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) \sum_{p=1}^N (z_p^2 - z_{p-1}^2) (\bar{Q}_{ij})_p \quad (18)$$

$$D_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{p=1}^N (z_p^3 - z_{p-1}^3) (\bar{Q}_{ij})_p \quad (19)$$

Hence the stiffness relationship and compliance relationship for a composite laminate could be expressed as follow:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} & \dots & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{13} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} & \dots & B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{23} \\ A_{32} & A_{32} & A_{33} & \dots & B_{32} & B_{32} & B_{33} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{13} & \dots & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{13} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} & B_{23} & \dots & D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{23} \\ B_{32} & B_{32} & B_{33} & \dots & D_{32} & D_{32} & D_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

The stiffness relationship and compliance relationship for a symmetrical composite laminate could be expressed as follow:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_{33} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{13} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & D_{21} & D_{22} & D_{23} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & D_{32} & D_{32} & D_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

The stiffness relationship and compliance relationship for a quasi-isotropic composite laminate could be expressed as follow:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & & & \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & 0 & & & \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}(A_{11} - A_{12}) & & & \\ & & \vdots & & & \\ & & & [B] & & \\ & & & & \dots & \\ & & & & & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

3 Structure DESIGN

3.1 Loading

The rear pressure bulkhead just withstands the cabin pressurization load, and the cabin pressure which is defined to be a positive load [4].

From the certification requirement, the pressurized compartment positive load,

$$P_{ultimate} = 2\Delta P \quad (23)$$

In this paper, $2\Delta P = 0.12 \text{ MPa}$.

The positive load is considered to be applied on the concave surface of dome to check the strength of rear pressure bulkhead.

The certification requirement also regulates that pressurized cabin needs two pressure differential relief valves which are used to prevent a negative pressure differential which maybe harms the aircraft structure. Niu, M. C. [1] advises that the upper limit of negative relief valve setting is 0.5psi which means that the pressure bulkhead should be oblige to withstand 0.5psi negative pressurization load.

$$\Delta P' = -0.5 \text{ psi} = -3447.5 \text{ Pa}$$

The Pressurized compartment negative load,

$$P'_{ultimate} = 2\Delta P' \quad (24)$$

Therefore, the negative pressurization load is more likely to lead to the buckling of domed pressure bulkheads.

3.2 Material Properties

In this paper, the author selects the CFRP composite material Hexcel 8852 IM7 which is a high performance CFRP that is widely used in aerospace structures as a result of its relative better impact resistance and damage tolerance for a wide range of applications. The properties of Hexcel 8852 IM7 are listed in table 2. [5] The Hexcel 8852 IM7 which is a high performance CFRP that is widely used in aerospace structures as a result of its relative better impact resistance and damage tolerance for a wide range of applications [6] [7].

Nominal Cured Ply Thickness	t	0.131 mm
Nominal Laminate Density	ρ	1.57 kg/cm ³
0 °Tensile Strength	X_t	2724 MPa
90 °Tensile Strength	Y_t	111 MPa
0 °Tensile Modulus	E_1	164 GPa
90 °Tensile Modulus	E_2	12 GPa
Shear modulus	G_{12}	5.8 GPa
0 °Compression Strength	X_c	1690 MPa
90 °Compression Strength	Y_c	250 MPa
In-plane Shear Strength	S	120 MPa
Poisson ratio	ν	0.28

Table 1: properties of Hexcel 8852 IM7

3.3 Laminate selection

The Vision of rear pressure bulkhead is designed according to pure membrane state of stress (no bending) which is same like a balloon or umbrella. The expected load case of skin of rear bulkhead is that the $N_\phi = N_t$ everywhere of the skin [8]. Figure 2 shows the expected load of dome skin.

Figure. 2 The expected load of dome skin

For the purpose of obtaining the constant stress and strain everywhere of the dome skin. A category of laminate is needed. Quasi-Isotropic Laminate is a balanced and symmetric laminate for which a constitutive property of interest, at a given point, displays isotropic behaviour in the plane of the laminate. A common quasi-isotropic laminates are like $(0/\pm 60)_s$ and $(0/\pm 45/90)_s$. Because of the infinite variability of the angular orientation of the individual lamina, one would assume that a laminate having a stiffness which behaves isotropically in the plane of the laminate could be constructed by using many plies having small, equal differences in their orientation [9].

A general rule for describing a quasi-isotropic laminate states that the angles between the plies are equal to π/N , where N is an integer greater than or equal to 3, and there is an identical number of plies at each orientation in a symmetric laminate. For plies of a given material, all such quasi-isotropic laminates will have the same elastic properties, regardless of the value of N [9].

A quasi-isotropic laminate has in-plane stiffnesses which follow isotropic relationships

$$E_x = E_y = E_\theta \quad (26)$$

Where the subscript θ indicates any arbitrary angle. Additionally,

$$G_{xy} = E_{xy}/[2(1 + \mu_{xy})] \quad (27)$$

The membrane properties are isotropic and identical for each of the laminates. Then the stiffness relationship and compliance relationship for a symmetrical and quasi-isotropic composite laminate could be expressed as follow [9]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2}(A_{11} - A_{12}) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 \\ k_x \\ k_y \\ k_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

In order to improve the performance of impact damage, using more $\pm 45^\circ$ plies and arranging the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies on the surface of the structure. Hence, the final stacking sequence of the dome skin is $(45/-45/0/90)_s$ which is a Quasi-isotropic laminate. The final stacking sequence of crack stoppers area is also $(45/-45/0/90)_s$.

3.4 Structure layout

Niu, M. C. [3] indicates that for the composite material, impact damage is the biggest threat of the structure instead of fatigue. The delamination of the structure is the critical damage of the composite material. The fatigue failure of composite materials is considered to occur gradually because of the

microscopic cracks exist during all the life time. For the tension-tension type loadings, the fatigue behaviour of composite material is superior to metal. For this reason, in this paper, the CFRP rear pressure bulkhead owns no stiffeners but a web crack stopper which is placed inner the dome skin laminate. But the crack propagation under the impact damage of composite is still a question for the composite rear pressure bulkhead. In this paper, the author designed a CFRP rear pressure bulkhead without stiffeners on the convex or the concave surface, but with the web shape CFRP crack stoppers intermediate the dome skin. The crack stopper is carved into web shape and uses the same CFRP material with the dome skin. The crack stopper not only can play a role in stop the crack from propagating but also has a function of stiffeners of dome skin. The skin of composite pressure bulkhead doesn't need to be cut into several pieces because of the whole skin can be manufactured in one piece. The final domed pressure bulkheads without and with stiffeners are displayed in Figure 3.

Figure. 3: domed pressure bulkheads structure without stiffeners

4 Finite Element Modelling and Analysis

All the parts are simplified into 2D shell element (Quad 4). The pressurization load is applied on the skin of the pressure bulkheads. Boundary condition is clamped support for the dome skin. For the buckling analysis, the load applied on the convex surface and the value is $2\Delta P' = 0.006895 \text{ MPa}$. The buckling happens at the peak of the cap. Figure 4 shows the domed bulkhead FEA models.

Figure. 4: domed bulkhead FEA models

4.1 Static analysis

The rear pressure bulkhead just withstands the cabin pressurization load, and the cabin pressure which is defined to be a positive load. Figure 5-7 are deflection, stress and strain contours of domed bulkheads without stiffeners under $2\Delta P$. The contours show that the edge of dome skin is the strain concentration area which should be paid more attention.

Figure 5: deflection contours of domed bulkheads without stiffeners under $2\Delta P$

Figure 6: strain contours of domed bulkheads without stiffeners under $2\Delta P$

Figure 7: stress contours of domed bulkheads without stiffeners under $2\Delta P$

Without stiffeners	
Strain	1003 $\mu\epsilon$
Stress	109.8Mpa
Deflection	2.32mm

Table 2: deflection and strain of domed bulkheads without stiffeners under $2\Delta P$

4.2 Buckling analysis

The buckling analysis is an Eigen value problem and the buckling load and buckling stress can be obtained from the Eigen value. The Eigen value is usually the first mode Eigen value which can predict the lowest critical buckling load and buckling stress. The Eigen value should be more than 1 when we design the structure. Table 3 shows eigenvalues of domed bulkheads without and with stiffeners under $2\Delta P$. Figure 7-8 display the contours of buckling analysis.

Figure. 7: 1st and 2nd eigenvalue of pressure bulkhead without stiffeners

Figure. 8: 3rd and 4th eigenvalue of pressure bulkhead without stiffeners

Without stiffeners	
1 st derivative	3.45
2 nd derivatives	3.46
3 rd derivatives	3.50
4 th derivatives	3.56

Table 3: eigenvalues of domed bulkheads without stiffeners under $2\Delta P$

5 Conclusion

From the results of static analysis, the strain of domed skin is $1003\mu\epsilon$ and the corresponding stress is 109.8Mpa, the maximum deflection is 2.32mm. For the composite bulkheads, the strain of each plies should be nearly $3500\mu\epsilon$. The strain of rear pressure bulkhead can meet the requirement of strength. The buckling happens at the peak of the cap. The FEA results approve that the crack stoppers contribute to improving the buckling performance and structure stability. The eigenvalue of the dome without stiffeners are acceptable. The composite domed rear pressure bulkhead without stiffeners could be treated as the best choice for the minimum mass and acceptable cost.

From the perspective of fatigue, the crack stoppers can stop the crack propagating. The circular and radial crack stoppers of rear pressure bulkheads have a function of reinforcement and can meets the

requirements of static strength. The crack stoppers on the composite rear pressure bulkhead have a positive influence on improvement of structure buckling performance. Hence, there is no need to arrange extra stiffeners on the dome skin.

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